

THE ROLE OF FINTECH STARTUPS IN ENHANCING REGIONAL FINANCIAL INCLUSION IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Annotation: This study looks at how fintech startups can help more people access financial services in the digital economy, with a focus on regional development. It emphasises the role of digital financial solutions, such as mobile payments, online banking, and locally developed fintech platforms, in enhancing access to financial services for individuals and enterprises. The study examines the Khorezm region to pinpoint significant obstacles, including inadequate digital infrastructure, low financial literacy, informal business practices, and trust deficits that hinder the successful implementation of fintech services. The results indicate that fintech startups are significant catalysts for financial inclusion by lowering transaction costs, enhancing accessibility, and boosting economic participation.

Key words: startup, finance, digital economy, financial inclusion, economic growth.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida fintech startaplarning moliyaviy xizmatlardan foydalanishni kengaytirishdagi rolini mintaqaviy rivojlanish nuqtai nazaridan tahlil qiladi. Unda mobil to'lovlar, onlayn bank xizmatlari va mahalliy ishlab chiqilgan fintech platformalar kabi raqamli moliyaviy yechimlarning aholi va biznes subyektlari uchun moliyaviy xizmatlardan foydalanishni kengaytirishdagi ahamiyati yoritiladi. Tadqiqot Xorazm viloyati misolida olib borilib, raqamli infratuzilmaning yetarli emasligi, moliyaviy savodxonlik darajasining pastligi, norasmiy biznes amaliyotlari hamda ishonch muammolari kabi fintech xizmatlarini samarali joriy etishga to'sqinlik qiluvchi asosiy muammolar aniqlanadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, fintech startaplar tranzaksiya xarajatlarini kamaytirish, xizmatlardan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish va iqtisodiy ishtirokni oshirish orqali moliyaviy inklyuziyaning muhim drayveri hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: startap, moliya, raqamli iqtisodiyot, moliyaviy inklyuziya, iqtisodiy o'sish.

Аннотация: Данное исследование рассматривает роль финтех-стартапов в расширении доступа к финансовым услугам в условиях цифровой экономики с акцентом на региональное развитие. В работе подчеркивается значение цифровых финансовых решений, таких как мобильные платежи, онлайн-банкинг и локально разработанные финтех-платформы, в повышении доступности финансовых услуг для населения и бизнес-субъектов. Исследование проводится на примере Хорезмской области и выявляет ключевые проблемы, включая недостаточно развитую цифровую инфраструктуру, низкий уровень финансовой грамотности, неформальные бизнес-практики, а также дефицит доверия, которые сдерживают эффективное внедрение финтех-услуг. Результаты показывают, что финтех-стартапы выступают важным драйвером финансовой инклюзии, снижая транзакционные издержки, повышая доступность услуг и способствуя расширению экономического участия.

Ключевые слова: стартап, финансы, цифровая экономика, финансовая инклюзия, экономический рост.

Sustainable regional economic development requires the creation of a favorable financial environment and the acceleration of digitalization processes within the economy. In this context, the extent to which both individuals and business entities utilize traditional and digital financial services serves as an important indicator of economic activity in the regions. The availability of broad access to financial services contributes to the development of entrepreneurial and business activities, expands access to financial resources, and enhances the transparency of economic

processes within regions. At the same time, this process can have a positive impact on reducing poverty levels and decreasing the size of the shadow economy.

Creating adequate conditions for the development of startup projects in the financial sector at the regional level, along with providing financial support to such initiatives, eventually leads to the emergence of fintech startups [6]. Notably, fintech startups expand the population's access to financial services and serve as a key driver in advancing financial inclusion. Namely, technologies such as mobile devices, cloud computing, big data analytics, artificial intelligence, and blockchain are enabling individuals to access financial products and services for the first time [9]. These services can be used anytime and from any location, offering a faster, more cost-effective, transparent, and efficient alternative to traditional banking systems. Prior to discussing the topic and examining existing research in the field, it is essential to provide clear definitions of the concepts of financial inclusion and fintech startups. Fintech, or financial technology, is a range of digital solutions, including mobile applications, software, and other technological tools, that enable individuals and businesses to access, manage, and deliver financial services in a digital format [4]. Accordingly, a fintech startup can be understood as a company primarily focused on developing and offering products and services based on financial technologies. Consequently, a fintech startup can be conceptualized as the intersection of finance, technology, and business activity, where innovative technological solutions are applied to deliver financial services (Figure 1).

Figure. 1. Conceptual Framework of Fintech Startups,Source: Developed by the author

On the other hand, financial inclusion refers to the ability of all individuals and business entities to freely access and effectively use appropriate financial services [2]. Financial inclusion is a multidimensional concept that encompasses factors related to digital development, consumer protection, market conduct, as well as gender and climate considerations [1]. It requires differentiated approaches for various target groups, including youth, small business entities, rural populations, forcibly displaced persons, and individuals with disabilities. In this context, it is essential to develop a deep understanding of the needs, preferences, and challenges of these groups, and to actively involve them in the process of designing appropriate solutions.

Financial inclusion also entails ensuring access to financial support. Technological advancements can facilitate access to short-term financing for individuals who are typically excluded from formal credit systems [3]. To simplify the lending process, creditors often rely on credit scoring mechanisms or startups that incorporate data such as credit card usage, repayment history, and mortgage payment records.

The development of financial markets and financial institutions in regions indicates a higher level of financial inclusion and positively contributes to economic growth. In turn, this process leads to a reduction in the size of the shadow economy. Therefore, implementing measures aimed at enhancing financial inclusion and improving financial literacy among the population in the regions is of significant importance [5].

A review of the existing academic literature reveals a number of theoretical approaches to financial inclusion. The most prominent among them include the public good theory, dissatisfaction theory, vulnerable group theory, systems theory, community echelon theory, public service theory, special agent theory, collaborative intervention theory, financial literacy theory, private money theory, public money theory, and intervention fund theory [7]. These theoretical

frameworks provide a comprehensive basis for systematically addressing the key challenges associated with financial inclusion.

Fintech startups leverage technologies such as digital payments, blockchain, artificial intelligence, and mobile banking to reduce transaction costs, lower barriers to market entry, and provide affordable, accessible, and tailored financial services to underserved populations. In doing so, they act as transformative and innovative agents within the financial system. The rapid growth in the number of fintech startups has significantly expanded access to credit, payments, savings, and investment services. This expansion contributes to increased economic participation, reduced inequality, poverty alleviation, and the promotion of gender equality [8]. Operating within supportive innovation ecosystems, fintech startups help democratize financial services, foster inclusive economic growth, and create new opportunities for disadvantaged groups. This study relies on a mixed-method approach, integrating descriptive analysis and qualitative assessment, to investigate the role of fintech startups in promoting financial inclusion at the regional level, specifically in the Khorezm region. The research uses secondary data sources, encompassing demographic statistics, reports on digital financial services, and existing academic literature pertaining to financial inclusion and fintech development. Furthermore, empirical observations regarding the utilisation of digital payment platforms, mobile banking applications, and ERP systems by individuals and enterprises were integrated to evaluate prevailing trends.

Analysis & Discussion. As of January 1, 2025, the population of the Khorezm region reached 2,032,398 people, with a notable demographic trend characterized by a relatively young population structure [10]. In particular, the number of individuals aged 0–2 was 138,811, those aged 3–5 amounted to 123,534, 6–7 years accounted for 75,499, and 8–15 years totaled 294,243, indicating a significant share of the younger generation. At the same time, the economically active population remains substantial, with 146,998 individuals aged 20–24, 156,358 aged 25–29, and 174,189 aged 30–34, reflecting the growing labor resource potential of the region. In contrast, the share of the population aged 60 and above is relatively lower (120,442 individuals aged 60–69, 29,169 aged 70–74, and 4,339 aged 80 and above), suggesting that younger and middle-aged groups represent the primary target segment for the adoption of digital financial services. Overall, the youth-dominated demographic structure of the region confirms the presence of favorable institutional and market conditions for expanding financial inclusion through fintech startups.

The population widely uses digital payment applications such as Click, Payme, Uzum Bank, Oson, and Paynet, which have become integral to everyday financial transactions. At the same time, the use of mobile banking applications for accessing financial services and products has increased significantly, reflecting the rapid digitalization of the financial sector. Notably, most banks now offer online microloans at varying interest rates, thereby expanding access to credit for individuals and small businesses.

In turn, businesses increasingly rely on ERP systems, with 1C remaining one of the most widely used platforms. In recent years, however, the expansion of the startup ecosystem has led to the emergence of locally developed fintech solutions created by domestic startups, which are now being actively adopted by enterprises. Examples include platforms such as Bito, Linko, Aqcha, and Acra, among others. These platforms are comparable to international solutions such as QuickBooks, Intuit, and Zoho Analytics, but are specifically adapted to local market conditions and regulatory requirements. Their adoption has improved financial management, accounting transparency, and operational efficiency among firms, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). As a result, such digital solutions contribute to enhancing financial inclusion at the firm level by facilitating access to financial services, improving record-keeping, and increasing the ability of businesses to obtain financing.

The research process identified a number of challenges and shortcomings faced by both the population and business entities (Table 1). Despite the increasing access to the internet, the quality of connectivity in remote areas of the region remains relatively low, which limits the effective use of fintech services. One of the most significant issues is the low level of financial literacy among

the population, particularly reflected in the limited ability to use digital banking and fintech applications. This problem is especially evident among older age groups.

At the same time, similar challenges are observed among small business owners and private entrepreneurs, who often maintain informal financial records and underreport income. In many cases, businesses still rely on manual, paper-based accounting practices. For both groups, a key barrier is the issue of trust, as individuals and business owners tend to lack confidence in digital financial services. This is largely due to the noticeable increase in online fraud in recent years, which has negatively affected the adoption of fintech solutions.

Table 1. Key Barriers to Financial Inclusion in the Khorezm Region

Problem	Affected Group	Brief Comment
Poor internet quality in remote areas	Both	Limits effective use of fintech and digital financial services despite increased access.
Low financial literacy	Individuals	Reduces understanding and usage of digital banking and fintech applications, especially among older populations.
Limited digital skills	Individuals	Lack of practical ability to use mobile banking and fintech platforms.
Informal financial practices	Businesses	Many SMEs operate without formal accounting and may underreport income.
Reliance on manual accounting	Businesses	Continued use of paper-based records reduces efficiency and transparency.
Low trust in digital financial services	Both	Concerns over security discourage adoption of fintech solutions.
Increase in online fraud	Both	Rising fraud cases undermine confidence in digital financial platforms.

Source: Developed by the author

Conclusion. Fintech startups are very important for making financial services more accessible in regional economies, especially now that digital transformation is happening. The Khorezm region's widespread use of digital payment platforms, mobile banking apps, and locally developed fintech solutions shows that more people and businesses are becoming part of the formal financial system. A number of policy steps are suggested to improve financial inclusion even more through the growth of fintech startups. First, it is important to improve digital infrastructure, especially in rural areas, to make sure that fintech services are always available. Second, there should be programs that specifically help people, especially older people, learn more about personal finance and how to use technology. Third, regulatory support for fintech startups, such as easier processes and frameworks that encourage innovation (like regulatory sandboxes), can help them grow. Fourth, it's important to build trust in digital financial services by making cybersecurity stronger and running public awareness campaigns. Finally, encouraging small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) to go digital, such as by using ERP and fintech solutions, can make financial information more open and make it easier for them to get formal loans.

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